

Pattern Recognition with Uncertain Data

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Abstract :

Pattern recognition, as a field of study, plays a pivotal role in identifying regularities or patterns within data, enabling businesses and organizations to make informed decisions, enhance productivity, and improve efficiency. Pythagorean fuzzy sets are very useful in providing a flexible model to elaborate uncertainty and vagueness involved in decision making problems. Based on the concept of distance between two objects and the information carried by the membership degrees, non-membership degrees and hesitancy degrees of Pythagorean fuzzy sets. This paper proposes the Euclidean distance measures between Pythagorean fuzzy sets in pattern recognition. Two numerical examples are considered to justify the elaborated method and to illustrate its viability and usefulness.

Keywords : Pythagorean fuzzy set; Euclidean distance measure, Pattern recognition problems.

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1. Introduction :

In the vast expanse of data-driven realms, the ability to discern patterns serves as an indispensable tool for making sense of the complexities around us. Pattern recognition, a fundamental concept bridging the realms of mathematics, computer science, and cognitive psychology, plays a pivotal role in various fields ranging from artificial intelligence to neuroscience. This article aims to delve into the essence of pattern recognition, exploring its significance, mechanisms, and diverse applications in contemporary society.

At its core, pattern recognition entails the identification of regularities or consistent features within data, allowing for the extraction of meaningful information. Whether it's recognizing familiar faces in a crowd, discerning linguistic patterns in texts, or detecting anomalies in financial transactions, humans and machines alike rely on pattern recognition mechanisms to navigate and comprehend the world. Pattern recognition encompasses a myriad of techniques and approaches, drawing inspiration from diverse disciplines such as statistics, machine learning, and signal processing. From simple heuristic methods to sophisticated neural network architectures, the mechanisms underlying pattern recognition span a spectrum of complexity.

Using a degree of membership, μ , Zadeh [21] devised the fuzzy set approach, to represent the degree of sense of belonging to the set under study, every component of the conceptual universe is renumbered from of the unit range [0, 1]. We designate a number from the unit range [0, 1] to each element of the discursive multiverse to signify the degree of sense of esteem and self - actualization to the set under study. Fuzzy sets are a subclass of set theory that allows for states that are midway between completeness and nothingness. To express the extent to which an element belongs to a class, a membership function is used in a fuzzy set. The worth of membership ranges from 0 to 1. The grade 0 is indicating that the element is not a member of the class, where by 1 indicating that it is, and additional considerations

indicating the level of participation. In crisp sets, the characteristic function was replaced with the amount of involvement. Since Zadeh's fundamental work, fuzzy set theory has been used to a wide range of fields, including artificial intelligence, signal processing, management sciences, engineering, mathematics, social sciences, automata theory, medical sciences, biology and statistics, etc.

Owing to the unavailability of non-membership functions as well as contempt for potential of indeterminacy margin, the idea of fuzzy sets theory seem to be unsatisfactory. To solve these inadequacies, the perception of intuitionistic fuzzy sets (IFSs) was developed by Atanassov [6]. The structures of IFSs combines the belonging function (μ), non-belongingness function (ν) and the indeterminacy margin (π) yielding $\mu + \nu \leq 1$ as well as $\mu + \nu + \pi = 1$. IFSs provide a structure that is adaptable for elaborating ambiguity and uncertainty.

Some situations where $\mu + \nu \geq 1$ exists, unlike in IFSs. Because of this necessity in IFSs, Pythagorean fuzzy sets were developed (PFSs). The Pythagorean fuzzy set (PFS), design in [18, 19] is a unique tool for dealing with ambiguity when evaluating membership grade and non-membership grade fulfilling the constraints $0 \leq \mu \leq 1$ and $0 \leq \nu \leq 1$, with the result that $\mu^2 + \nu^2 + \pi^2 = 1$. PFSs are better at characterizing unclear data than IFSs. When it comes to mimicking real-world confusion, PFS trumps IFS by a wide margin.

Multi-criteria decision analysis has been widely investigated and successfully applied to many fields of real world problems. Adak et al. [1] discussed on new ranking approach to solve MCDM problems with generalized intuitionistic fuzzy information. Shinoj et al. [12] applied intuitionistic fuzzy sets in medical diagnosis. Garg [10] invented on new generalized Pythagorean fuzzy information aggregation using Einstein operations and its application to decision making. Senapati et al. [13] applied Fermatean fuzzy WPM in multiple criteria decision making. Szmidt et al. [14] used similarity measure for Intuitionistic fuzzy sets in medical diagnostic. Pattern recognition is the one of the decision making problems. In his paper, we discussed on career detection by pattern recognition based on Euclidean distance measurement.

The following is how the rest of the paper is organized. Section 2 review preliminaries and definitions intuitionistic fuzzy sets, Pythagorean fuzzy sets and

some operations on Pythagorean fuzzy sets. Euclidean distance measures between Pythagorean fuzzy sets are discussed and apply this measure in pattern recognition problems in Section 3. At the end, conclusion is laid out in Section 4.

2. Preliminaries and Definitions :

We will go over the ideas that are connected to fuzzy sets, Pythagorean fuzzy sets and intuitionistic fuzzy sets in this section.

Definition 1 : [21] We defined fuzzy set F in a universal set X as $F = \{\langle x, \mu_F(x) \rangle : x \in X\}$, where $\mu_F: X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a mapping that is known as the fuzzy membership function.

The complement of μ is defined by $\bar{\mu}(x) = 1 - \mu(x)$ for all $x \in X$ and denoted by $\bar{\mu}$.

Definition 2 : [6] An intuitionistic fuzzy set (IFS) A in X is defined as $A = \{\langle x, \alpha_A(x), \beta_A(x) \rangle : x \in X\}$, where the $\alpha_A(x)$ is the worth of membership and $\beta_A(x)$ is the worth of non-membership of the element $x \in X$ respectively.

Also $\alpha_A: X \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $\beta_A: X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ and satisfy the condition $0 \leq \alpha_A(x) + \beta_A(x) \leq 1$, for all $x \in X$.

The degree of indeterminacy $h_A(x) = 1 - \alpha_A(x) - \beta_A(x)$.

In some circumstances $0 \leq \mu(x) + \nu(x) \leq 1$ for whatever reason, this may not be the case. We take some situations where $0.7 + 0.5 = 1.2 > 1$, but $0.7^2 + 0.5^2 < 1$. Again, $0.6 + 0.6 = 1.2 > 1$, but $0.6^2 + 0.6^2 < 1$. To deal with this problem, Yager proposed the perspective assumes of Pythagorean fuzzy set in 2013.

Definition 3 : [18] A Pythagorean fuzzy set P in universe of discourse X is represented as $P = \{\langle x, \alpha_P(x), \beta_P(x) \rangle | x \in X\}$, where $\alpha_P(x): X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ denotes the worth of membership and $\beta_P(x): X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ represents the worth to which the element $x \in X$ is not a member of the set P , with the condition that $0 \leq (\alpha_P(x))^2 + (\beta_P(x))^2 \leq 1$, for all $x \in X$.

The worth of indeterminacy $h_P(x) = \sqrt{1 - (\alpha_P(x))^2 - (\beta_P(x))^2}$.

Some Operations on Pythagorean Fuzzy Sets :

Here we presents some basic operations of Pythagorean fuzzy sets.

- (i) $A^c = \{\langle x, v_A(x), \mu_A(x) : x \in X \rangle\}$
- (ii) $A \cup B = \{\langle x, \max(\mu_A(x), \mu_B(x)), \min(v_A(x), v_B(x)) \rangle : x \in X\}$
- (iii) $A \cap B = \{\langle x, \min(\mu_A(x), \mu_B(x)), \max(v_A(x), v_B(x)) \rangle : x \in X\}$
- (iv) $A \oplus B = \{\langle x, (\mu_A(x) + \mu_B(x) - \mu_A(x)\mu_B(x)), v_A(x)v_B(x) \rangle : x \in X\}$
- (v) $A \otimes B = \{\langle x, \mu_A(x)\mu_B(x), v_A(x) + v_B(x) - v_A(x)v_B(x) \rangle : x \in X\}$
- (vi) $A - B = \{\langle x, \min(\mu_A(x)v_B(x)), \max(v_A(x)\mu_B(x)) \rangle : x \in X\}$
- (vii) $A \times B = \{\langle x, \mu_A(x)\mu_B(x), v_A(x)v_B(x) \rangle : x \in X\}$.

3. Distance measurement of Pythagorean Fuzzy Sets :

Definition 4 : (Property of distance) Any set X whose elements are called points is said to be a metric space if for any two points $A, B \in X$, there is an associated real number $d(A, B)$ called distance if the following properties hold true:

- (i) $d(A, B) \geq 0$, (non-negativity)
- (ii) $d(A, B) = 0 \Leftrightarrow A = B$ (definiteness)
- (iii) $d(A, B) = d(B, A)$ (symmetry)
- (iv) $d(A, C) \leq d(A, B) + d(B, C)$, for any $B \in X$ (triangle inequality).

Any functions with all these properties are called distance functions, or distance measures.

Definition 5 : The Euclidean distance $d_E(A_1, A_2)$ between two Pythagorean fuzzy number A_1 and A_2 is defined as

$$d_E(A_1, A_2) = \left[\left(\mu_{A_1}^2(x_i) - \mu_{A_2}^2(x_i) \right)^2 + \left(v_{A_1}^2(x_i) - v_{A_2}^2(x_i) \right)^2 + \left(\pi_{A_1}^2(x_i) - \pi_{A_2}^2(x_i) \right)^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

$$X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}, \text{ for } i = 1, 2, \dots, n \tag{1}$$

Definition 6 : The normalized Euclidean distance $d_{NE}(A, B)$ between two Pythagorean Fuzzy Sets A and B is defined as

$$d_{NE}(A, B) = \left(\frac{1}{2n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\left(\mu_A^2(x_i) - \mu_B^2(x_i) \right)^2 + \left(\nu_A^2(x_i) - \nu_B^2(x_i) \right)^2 + \left(\pi_A^2(x_i) - \pi_B^2(x_i) \right)^2 \right] \right)^{1/2}$$

$$X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}, \text{ for } i = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (2)$$

Example 1 : We consider the pattern recognition problem with four patterns C_1, C_2, C_3, C_4 which are represented by the following Pythagorean fuzzy sets in the given finite universe $X = \{x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4\}$, respectively:

$$C_1 = \{(x_1, 0.6, 0.5), (x_2, 0.8, 0.5), (x_3, 0.6, 0.6), (x_4, 0.4, 0.8)\}$$

$$C_2 = \{(x_1, 0.6, 0.4), (x_2, 0.7, 0.3), (x_3, 0.5, 0.7), (x_4, 0.5, 0.6)\}$$

$$C_3 = \{(x_1, 0.6, 0.5), (x_2, 0.6, 0.4), (x_3, 0.7, 0.5), (x_4, 0.5, 0.7)\}$$

$$C_4 = \{(x_1, 0.5, 0.7), (x_2, 0.4, 0.7), (x_3, 0.3, 0.8), (x_4, 0.6, 0.7)\}$$

Given an unknown pattern Q , which is represented by the Pythagorean fuzzy sets.

$$Q = \{(x_1, 0.4, 0.8), (x_2, 0.6, 0.6), (x_3, 0.5, 0.6), (x_4, 0.7, 0.6)\}.$$

The task is to classify the pattern Q in one of the attributes C_1, C_2, C_3 and C_4 .

According to the recognition principle, minimum normalized Euclidean distance between Q and $C_i, i = 1, 2, 3, 4$ will be proper classified pattern of Q .

The process of assigning the pattern Q to C_i is described by

$$k = \min_{1 \leq i \leq 4} \{d_{NE}(C_i, Q)\} \quad (3)$$

By Eq. (2), we can compute the normalized distance measure between $C_i, (i = 1, 2, 3, 4)$ with Q .

Therefore, $d_{NE}(C_1, Q) = 0.1766, d_{NE}(C_2, Q) = 0.1804, d_{NE}(C_3, Q) = 0.1684$ and $d_{NE}(C_4, Q) = 0.1338$.

Hence, we can conclude that the pattern Q should be classified in C_4 , according to the recognition rule given by Eq. (3).

Example 2 : Here, we use normalized Euclidean distance measurement method of Pythagorean fuzzy sets in career determination problems by the students for his/her further study. Let us consider a set of attribute $C = \{C_1, C_2, C_3, C_4\}$, and criteria related to attributes are $S = \{S_1, S_2, S_3, S_4, S_5\}$.

The following table shows careers and related subjects requirements:

$$C_1 = \{(S_1, 0.8, 0.3), (S_2, 0.5, 0.4), (S_3, 0.7, 0.5), (S_4, 0.9, 0.1), (S_5, 0.4, 0.5)\}$$

$$C_2 = \{(S_1, 0.7, 0.3), (S_2, 0.8, 0.5), (S_3, 0.7, 0.6), (S_4, 0.6, 0.4), (S_5, 0.8, 0.3)\}$$

$$C_3 = \{(S_1, 0.6, 0.4), (S_2, 0.7, 0.4), (S_3, 0.6, 0.5), (S_4, 0.5, 0.6), (S_5, 0.6, 0.4)\}$$

$$C_4 = \{(S_1, 0.7, 0.5), (S_2, 0.6, 0.3), (S_3, 0.5, 0.4), (S_4, 0.8, 0.3), (S_5, 0.5, 0.4)\}$$

Each performance is described by Pythagorean fuzzy numbers that consists of membership and non-membership grades. After various examination and assessments a particular attribute (say P) performance in different criteria are represented by Pythagorean fuzzy numbers as follows:

$$P = \{(S_1, 0.6, 0.4), (S_2, 0.5, 0.3), (S_3, 0.7, 0.2), (S_4, 0.7, 0.4), (S_5, 0.5, 0.4)\}$$

Our aim is to determine the student P belong to which attributes of C_i ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4$). The recognition rule given as follows:

$$k = \min_{1 \leq i \leq 4} \{d_{NE}(C_i, P)\} \quad (4)$$

Then we assign attributes P to the particular attribute.

By the Eq. (2), we can obtain the normalized Euclidean distance as follows:

$$d_{NE}(C_1, P) = 0.3467, d_{NE}(C_2, P) = 0.1550, d_{NE}(C_3, P) = 0.1584 \text{ and } d_{NE}(C_4, P) = 0.1707.$$

Hence, we can assign the attribute P to the attribute C_2 , according to the recognition rule given by Eq. (4).

Conclusion :

Pattern recognition stands as a cornerstone of modern computational intelligence, unraveling hidden insights within data and empowering human decision-making processes. As technology continues to advance, the frontier of pattern recognition expands, promising new avenues for innovation and discovery. By fostering interdisciplinary collaboration and harnessing the synergy between human cognition and machine learning, we can unlock the full potential of pattern recognition to tackle real-world challenges and pave the way for a more intelligent future.

We will look into the decision-making process more in the future using interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy sets uncertain data.

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Conflicts of Interest :

The authors declare that there is no competing of interests.

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